

Z-PINS RESISTING MODE I DYNAMIC DELAMINATION IN WOVEN LAMINATE

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SUMMARY

Dynamic Mode I delamination initiation in a z-pinned woven composite laminate is studied using a Wedge Insertion Fracture (WIF) method on a Kolsky Bar apparatus. It is shown that there exists a positive correlation between fracture initiation load and loading rate for all loading rates and z-pin diameters studied.

Keywords: Z-pinned composites, Dynamic delamination, Kolsky bar

INTRODUCTION

Composite materials have slowly gained acceptance as a structural material of choice for weight-critical applications. This acceptance has been somewhat hampered, however, by the tendency of composite materials to fail in modes uncommon in more conventional materials, such as delamination. During a delamination failure, a crack forms and propagates between different layers in a laminate, preventing load from being efficiently transferred between layers and degrading the material's performance. In recent decades, there has been much interest in composite methods which would help prevent the formation of delamination cracks and hinder existing cracks' propagation.

Among the most popular are stitching [1] and z-pinning [2, 3]. Z-pinning, while a newer techniques, holds many advantages over stitching. Z-pinning can be done on a prepreg layup in commercial quantities with minimal fiber damage [2], unlike stitching, which must be done in the preform state or risk significant damage to the fibers [1]. In addition, the z-pins can be inserted into a prepreg layup directly on the die, since it requires only one-sided access to the laminate. Preliminary studies on the effect of z-pinning on Mode I fracture toughness showed it doubled for every 0.5% increase in the areal density of z-pins [4].

Z-pinning increases Mode I fracture toughness at quasi-static rates, but there has been almost no study of their fracture properties in the dynamic case. Since a significant portion of delamination damage in practice is due to impact damage, the possibility of changes in the fracture properties of z-pinned composites at impact rates should be of great concern. To the authors' knowledge, the only work on dynamic delamination in z-pinned composites was performed by Liu et al. [5] using standard double cantilever

beam specimens in an Instron universal machine. This study uses a modified Kolsky bar (or split Hopkinson pressure bar) setup to more closely approximate impact rates in order to examine possible loading-rate effects on Mode I fracture initiation in z-pinned laminates. This is an expansion on our previously published study [6]; this paper contains results based on an expanded data set including specimens with different diameter z-pins.

MATERIALS AND SPECIMEN PREPARATION

The laminate material tested in this study consisted of a 24 oz per square yard, 5x5 plain weave fabric of AGY 463 S-2 glass, with a CYCOM 381 epoxy matrix. The laminate consists of 16 prepreg layers laid up in a $[0]_{16}$ arrangement, with a 50 μm thick Teflon layer placed at the midplane along two opposite edges of each plate to form the pre-crack for the testing. Into this laminate layup were inserted pultruded carbon-fiber z-pins. There were two types of z-pins: 0.5 mm diameter z-pins made from T650 carbon fiber and 0.3 mm diameter z-pins made from T300 carbon fiber, both with a CYCOM 5250-4 BMI resin matrix. These z-pins were each inserted into plates in three different densities: 1%, 2%, and 4% by volume. Thus there were seven different sample materials: 0.3 mm z-pins and 0.5 mm z-pins each in 1%, 2%, and 4% densities, as well as a control plate with no z-pins. After z-pin insertion, the plates were cured.

The cured plates were machined into specimens for testing using a water jet cutter. The specimens were approximately 110 mm x 20 mm x 11.5 mm, with the long axis of the specimen in the 0° direction. Each specimen was machined with a 90° notch on the pre-crack end, with the Teflon film extending approximately 5 mm beyond the notch tip. The sample's pinned region began at the end of the pre-crack and extended the length of the specimen. Each specimen also had four conductive-paint gauges (crack detection gauges) to monitor crack propagation. The first of these crack detection gauges was placed at the tip of the pre-crack to detect fracture initiation. The details of specimen geometry are displayed in Fig. 1.

Figure 1: Details of the specimen geometry.

EXPERIMENTAL PROCEDURE

The specimens were loaded dynamically using the Kolsky bar apparatus shown in Fig. 2, using a WIF method based on that proposed by Sun and Han [7]. The Kolsky bar setup consisted of the pressure gun, the bars (striker, incident, and transmission bars), and the data acquisition system, as well as a high-speed camera (not shown). The striker, incident, and transmission bars were all steel of 19 mm diameter. The length of the striker bar was 610 mm, the incident bar 4.2 m, and the transmission bar 1.37 m. A pair of resistor strain gages was mounted on the incident bar 1.33 m from its specimen end, and a pair of semiconductor strain gages was mounted on the transmission bar 300 mm from its specimen end. A 5-mm diameter soft copper disk pulse shaper was mounted between the striker bar and the incident bar. The thickness of the pulse shaper and the air gun firing pressure were varied in an attempt to generate different loading rates. The thickness of the pulse shaper was 1.1 mm for those tests with a firing pressure of 15 or 20 psi, and 1.6 mm for a firing pressure of 30 or 40 psi. The pulse shapers also damp oscillations that would otherwise appear in the plateau region of the incident pulse.

Figure 2: Kolsky bar apparatus.

To apply WIF loading, the loading wedge displayed in Fig. 3 was used. During testing, the rounded end of the wedge was placed in the specimen's notch, while the flat end of the specimen was supported against the face of the transmission bar, shown in Fig. 4. The specimen was then loaded by driving the loading wedge into the specimen's notch, which resulted in the propagation of the interlaminar fracture.

Figure 3: Loading wedge front view (left) and side view (right).

Figure 4: Fracture specimen mounted in Kolsky bar testing apparatus

The strain gage pairs on the bar surfaces were connected to Wheatstone bridges excited at 28V, the output of which was sent through a Tektronix ADA400A differential preamplifier to the Tektronix TDS 420A oscilloscope. The crack detection gauges were connected to the circuit depicted in Fig. 5. This circuit, identical to that used by Syn [8], condensed the output to two channels such that the circuit output 5 V when all were intact, 2.5 V when the first gauge in a pair fractured, and 0 V when both gauges in a pair fractured. The oscilloscope and high speed camera (Cordin 550) were synchronized to capture the fracture process.

Figure 5: Crack detection gauge circuit schematic

DATA REDUCTION AND ANALYSIS

During each (dynamic) test, the voltage outputs of the transmission bar strain gage pair and the two crack gauge circuits, the time of each voltage reading, and photographs of the fracture process were recorded using the high-speed camera. A typical set of raw data is presented below in Figs. 6 through 8.

Figure 6: Typical transmission bar strain gage signal

Figure 7: Typical crack detection gauge signal

Figure 8: Typical high-speed photographs of the fracture event. Zero time is the beginning of the load pulse

In data reduction, the signal from the transmission bar strain gage pair must be re-zeroed. Looking at Fig. 6, one can see that the signal goes from approximately zero volts before the trigger to around 0.01 volts shortly thereafter, but long before the actual load pulse arrives. This was due to interference from the flash for the high-speed camera. This interference has been well characterized, and does not decay over the time period of interest, so the approximately 0.01 volts of the constant interference can easily be subtracted from the signal. This signal is then converted into a load trace using standard strain gage methods.

Figure 9: Typical trace of load on specimen and crack gauge voltages near time of fracture initiation

Because the transmission bar strain gage pair is 300 mm from the specimen, the transmission signal must be time-shifted by 61 μs such that it describes the load on the

specimen at a given time. This synchronizes the crack gauge data and the specimen load trace, as shown in Fig. 9.

The photographs from the high-speed camera must be synchronized with the oscilloscope data. As shown in Fig. 9, on some specimens the signal from the fracture of the first crack gauge was quite noisy. To synchronize the photos with the oscilloscope data, the least ambiguous fracture of a gauge was taken as the benchmark to determine the time of fracture for the first crack gauge using the photos and the known frame rate, even when the first crack gauge data is inconclusive.

Finally, the loading rate for each specimen was calculated. The loading rate is taken to be the slope of the linearly increasing portion prior to the first peak of the specimen load trace. This was calculated by performing a linear regression on the linear portion of the specimen load trace.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Using the method discussed above, it was discovered that fracture initiated in the majority of specimens near the first peak load in the specimen load trace. This peak load is therefore taken to be the fracture initiation load.

It should be noted that the nature of the “fracture initiation” phenomenon captured at this peak load is unclear. It could be the initial delamination fracture, the debonding of the initial row of z-pins, or a combination of both. The current data set does not contain sufficient information to differentiate between the two. However, it is likely that this corresponds to the debonding of the first row of pins, as it is generally accepted that z-pins have little or no effect on the initiation of short cracks [2]. There was also slight necking observed in some crack gauges during fracture by the high-speed photographs, indicating that a non-trivial crack opening displacement is required to fracture the crack gauges, which is unlikely to occur without debonding the initial row of z-pins.

Figure 10 depicts the relationship between Mode I fracture initiation load and loading rate for 0.5 mm diameter z-pins, while Fig. 11 depicts the same relationship for 0.3 mm diameter z-pins. It can be easily seen from Figs. 10 and 11 that there is a positive correlation between loading rate and fracture load for all pin densities and pin diameters tested and that specimens containing z-pins all have higher fracture loads than those without at comparable loading rates. Figure 10 also shows a general trend that a higher volume percentage of 0.5 mm z-pins tends to lead to a higher fracture load, though the data is only suggestive on this point. That relationship between fracture load and pin density for the 0.5 mm z-pin specimens is displayed in Fig. 12. It shows a clear positive correlation between pin density and fracture load, but due to the inability to ensure an even distribution of loading rates, the seemingly conclusive relationship shown in Fig. 12 should be taken only as a tentative suggestion, which we intend to further investigate.

Figure 10: Relationship between fracture load and loading rate for different densities of 0.5 mm z-pins

Figure 11: Relationship between fracture load and loading rate for different densities of 0.3 mm z-pins

Figure 12: Relation between pin density and fracture load for 0.5 mm z-pins

It is of note that Fig. 11 does not seem to suggest the trend of higher volume percentage of z-pins leading to a higher fracture load for 0.3 mm z-pins which was found for 0.5 mm z-pins, and that the 4% pin density values have been left off of Fig. 11 completely. This is due to poor specimen quality for the 0.3 mm z-pin composites. Figure 13 shows a typical sample of 4% pin density of 0.5 mm pins alongside a sample with 0.3 mm pins. It can be easily seen that while the 0.5 mm pins have been driven through the entirety of the laminate, the 0.3 mm pins have been driven only slightly more than halfway through. This renders us unable to compare data across pin sizes, as the length of the pin which needs to be debonded as part of the fracture process is wildly varying between the two pin sizes. The higher the pin density, the shallower the pin penetration was for the 0.3 mm z-pins, which also renders it impossible to compare across pin densities due to the variation in necessary pin debond length.

Figure 13: A comparison of the z-pin depth in a specimen of 4% 0.5 mm z-pins (left) with a specimen of 4% 0.3 mm z-pins (right). Note that the 0.5 mm pins penetrate fully, while the 0.3 mm pins go only approximately halfway through.

Figure 14 shows a typical specimen with 4% pin density of 0.3 mm z-pins following fracture. It can be clearly seen that the specimen's crack did not propagate along the centerline of the composite in line with the pre-crack. It instead propagated through another portion of the composite, avoiding the pinned region altogether. The majority of 4% pin density of 0.3 mm z-pin specimens fractured in this manner. While this phenomenon does show qualitatively that the z-pins are quite effective at resisting Mode I dynamic delamination, initiating a new crack was not the objective of the experiment, and the data from these specimens cannot be usefully compared with the data from the other pin densities, where delamination occurred following the intended path extending from the pre-crack along the specimen's midplane.

Figure 14: A typical specimen with 4% pin density of 0.3 mm pins following fracture. Note that the fracture did not follow the specimen midplane as intended, but it instead initiated a new fracture along the laminar interface immediately below the z-pins.

CONCLUSIONS

Dynamic Mode I delamination initiation in a z-pinned woven composite laminate was studied. A positive correlation between loading rate and fracture initiation load for both z-pin sizes and all z-pin densities tested was determined. The data suggest that higher z-pin densities lead to a higher fracture load, though further study is needed.

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